

Underwater Acoustic Sensor Network & Soft Computing Techniques- Critical Review Study

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Abstract: Wireless Networks that lack proper infrastructure and that are also self-configured in nature together form Wireless Sensor Networks abbreviated as WSN. They can be employed for monitoring of conditions in the environment including temperature as well as pressure. Followed by this stage, the monitoring data passes from the source to destination for carrying out the analysis process. Gathering of sensor data is done from undersea and they together constitute the Underwater WSN. The destination node called sink node receives the data collected and the communication can also be done with the help of acoustic waves. Current research work critically analyzes the state of the art of such systems.

Keywords: Wireless Networks, Wireless Sensor Networks, sensor data, Underwater WSN, Ccommunication

I. Introduction

Due to various disadvantages of electromagnetic waves such as more power for transmission and at the same time attenuation is also higher. Acoustic waves incur lower attenuation along with higher reliability. Sensor nodes as well as control nodes constitute the UWSN architecture. Gathering of data is done with the help of sensor nodes that are deployed underwater and their communication is taken care of by the modems. Data among these nodes get transferred with the help of acoustic modems. Node deployment employs several strategies as they use batteries for supplying power to the nodes. Storage is handled by the nodes that are deployed and the communication takes place using acoustic modems.

When the architecture of UWSN is two dimensional, the following components are involved, (i) sensors, (ii) surface stations, (iii) vehicles for underwater movement. The major function of acoustic modem in underwater WSN is data gathering and transmission. Their operation is dependent on batteries. A transceiver helps in the process of data collection and sends the data to sink nodes. Surface station obtains data by usage of a transceiver for sending the data. These stations in turn employ RF signals for communication among the sinks located both on shore as well as surface level. This communication can

be done with the help of links that are available directly or by paths which may be multi-hop ones. Data transmission occurs in a direct way with the sink while the sensors employ direct link. In terms of energy efficiency, however, it falls short. On the other hand, intermediate nodes relay the data between source and the destination nodes in case multi-hop links.

One of the significant underwater robots is an AUV called an Autonomous Underwater Vehicle and the computer that is remote is able to control it. As they are not dependent on human beings as well as they are not specific to a particular location, they were named as autonomous. UUV stands for Unmanned Underwater Vehicle and is also called AUV. Their movement can be done in a freeway and batteries are utilized for providing the power. Additionally, they have cameras as well as antennas including profilers and so on. Few other vehicles are also larger in size and have cells based on aluminum. In the year 1871, Rovert Whitehead was the name of the scientist and the Automobile Fish Torpedo was developed as a missile. Preys are attacked by the shocks emitted by electric ray fish and hence the name came. AUV shape also resembles the torpedo ones as the size along with design is usable in nature. Their sizes also vary as they can also be portable. Table 1.3. Shows the applications of AUV based on their size.

Fig. 1 UWSN Components

A sensor node in UWSN has the following components as shown in Fig 1.

- Controller - Interfacing of sensor is done with the controller.
- CPU - Sensor data is sent to the CPU, followed by storage and processing. Using an acoustic modem, data is forwarded to the following sensor.
- Supply of power - Necessary for proper functioning of sensors in any medium.
- Sensor protection - A covering is provided for the sensors to prevent failures that are caused by corrosion.

UWSN differs from the terrestrial ones on the basis of node deployment, network architecture, and node reliability along with localization. Data collection is done by the nodes in UWSN and in turn they help in locating the place from where the data is being fetched. Notifications for hazards can be sent based on this data and help in saving human life. As the function of nodes is based on the data collected, data source is also necessary which makes localization an important factor. Technologies such as Global Positioning System termed as GPS are not suitable for UWSN due to acoustic communication. Network reliability maintenance is difficult as changes can occur underwater suddenly. Based on these factors, researchers focus on UWSN routing to maintain reliability, improve the lifetime of the network as well as increase energy efficiency.

The route process is basically a routine to face challenges that happened in restricted bandwidth. Therefore, underwater monitoring is one among the challenges that can be handled using WSNs. There are many facilities such as vehicle processes organizing the movement using AUV. Also added with the data storage as distribution collection based on tasks performed is one among the ground surrounded levels or stations. UWSN has many physical issues such as bandwidth less, delay in time frame, more propagation with time delay, topological selection, MAC control, router techniques and also higher power requirement. Moreover, utilizing all the available resources is also a performance task that is to be monitored in UWSN. Medium access protocols such as collision, frequency, time or spectrum are also one of the communities that can handle many Artificial intelligences (AI). The powerful domain in AI has been enlightened by including Machine and Deep learning in all real time applications where Deep learning can show its various characteristics that apply routing protocols. Deep learning deals with sensor nodes which are primary for underwater WSN which are of types of nodes sink, vehicles sensor nodes as AUV. Sink nodes might increase based on the multihop path communication, also the network can hold more sinks which grows with the parallel sensor nodes which can sense various inputs from data nodes that are frequently mentioned as packets in the entire UWSN architecture.

A. Beetle Antennae Search (BAS) Optimization Algorithm

The working of the algorithm is based on the beetles with antennae which are longer in length. From the beetle family, the ones with long horns are long compared to the body of a beetle. Their antenna is one of the important organs of the body. The presence of receptor cells makes these species unique among all and the main functionality includes identification of prey along

with pheromone generation. The area of detection is enlarged with the help of these antennas and also acts as a mechanism for warning. During the movement of beetles, there is wobbling of their antennas for receiving the odor of prey and also for identification of partners. The neighboring areas are detected in a random manner. One of the antennas identifies the prey and the other one finds the direction of movement. The optimization of objective function is performed depending on the behavior of searching for beetles. This makes an effective optimization algorithm for obtaining optimum results.

II. Literature Review on Underwater Communication

Communication that happens underwater is applicable for various domains and its demand is being increased nowadays (Zhong et al. 2011). In order to communicate in UWSN, an acoustic modem is being employed.

Research focus is towards improving the consumption of power, cost of data rate and modem size (Ian et al. 2005). Multiplexing techniques are employed in these modems to provide communication in an effective way. As this environment is dependent on water, the design process becomes a tedious task (Nusrat et al. 2016). Expenditure incurred for the process is increased even when the communication is for a shorter range. Processes such as transmission as well as receiving the data becomes difficult. In a few situations, the antenna is used in an omnidirectional way where the nodes need to coordinate (Keyu et al. 2014). These pitfalls are managed in the proposed work based on the survey done with the existing systems.

A. Sensor Nodes in Underwater

The components used for communication performed underwater include the unit for sensing, communication, unit for supplying power, as well as unit for processing (Muhammad et al. 2017). Temperature along with pressure are the physical conditions to be considered. The collected data conversion as signals is performed and the acoustic modem takes care of communication methods.

B. Existing Works

In UWSN, the proposed model created CUWUSN (Bhattacharjya et al. 2022) called as Cluster based Underwater Wireless Sensor Network which plays a major role in monitoring as well as controlling. The major requirement for UWSN includes the lifetime of the network being improved. The protocol aims at reducing the expenditure incurred for the energy of the nodes. The features of the proposed model include the selection of the head for a cluster along with the transmission in a multi-hop manner. This type of transmission improves the lifetime of the entire network. Based on the simulation results, the model is analyzed using various parameters such as delivery of packets, delay in transmission, consumption of energy and throughput of the network and so on. The routing protocol which outperforms in CUWUSN is AODV thereby proving the efficiency of the network.

Various challenges of UWSN include bandwidth that is being limited, attenuation being increased, power of battery being reduced and attenuation being higher. Internet of Things has

been employed in combination with UWSN to explore underwater environments. They are also utilized for military as well as scientific purposes. Communication among nodes in UWSN also faces various problems. The major requirement of UWSN is consumption of energy in an increased manner, delay needs to be decreased and lifetime of the network needs to be minimized for effective communication. In order to achieve these milestones, BES algorithm (Kapileswar & Phani. 2022) termed as Bald Eagle Search is utilized for the purpose of routing. This optimization algorithm is nature-based which

inspired the behavior of hunting of bald eagles. The protocol works on three phases namely (i) phase of initialization, (ii) phase of construction and (iii) phase for transmission of data. Identification of location is performed in the first phase. Second phase is further subdivided as selection of nearby nodes and finding of path for routing. The node with more residual energy is chosen for broadcasting the data for the whole network. The results obtained after implementing in MATLAB prove that the algorithm performs better in UWSN. Table 1 shows the techniques for deployment in UWSN.

Table 1 Techniques for Deployment in UWSN

Type of Deployment	Observation	Applications	Disadvantages
Static	Overlap Problems minimization	Monitoring Pollution	Complexity increases with coverage
Static	Maximization of Lifetime for Network	Propagation delay is avoided	Complexity in computation
Self-Adjustment	Deployment in areas that are uncovered	Nodes to be redeployed	Energy being consumed is more
Self-Adjustment	Coverage of Network Improvement	Improve the coverage issues	Energy consumed is increased
Based on Movement	Reduction of distance along with time	Balancing of load, Aggregation of data	Energy consumed is increased
Based on Movement	Reduction of time taken for travel	Environmental factors monitoring	Complexity in computation, Energy consumed is increased

The components of UWSN are sensor nodes, buoy available at the surface of water, nodes for anchoring as well as AUV. These are the components used for monitoring the underwater environment. The applications of UWSN includes navigational purposes, exploration activities to be conducted offshore, collection of data from oceans, monitoring of pollution, prevention of disaster and applications related to surveillance (Panchal et al. 2022). On the other hand, issues related with UWSN are supply of power being limited, constraints on computation and communication done underwater. These problems can be handled when the network is partitioned and the cluster heads are selected. For this selection process, fuzzy logic systems are employed along with handling of issues related to packet routing as well as security.

Data needs to be transmitted in a reliable manner while considering UWSN as a communication medium plays a significant role here. The proposed model KACO stands for K-means with Ant Colony Optimization (Qiuchan et al. 2022) divides the area as layers based on the level of depth. Clusters are formed with the help of the K-means algorithm in addition to the selection of cluster heads. This selection process utilizes node energy with the sink distance for computation purposes. For routing that occurs in intercluster, ACO is utilized where the coefficient termed as Gini is employed to improvise the results. The proposed work reduces the consumption of energy for all

nodes along with efficiency improvement in transmission of packets.

The applications of UWSN include management of disasters, prediction of water quality, observance of the environment and navigation performed underwater. Observation of the underwater environment is performed using sensors located in the rivers or oceans. This makes the sensors to be energy restricted and replacement with batteries becomes a difficult task. This makes efficiency of energy to become one of the significant problems in UWSN. Routing protocols depending on formation of clusters suffer from certain limitations related to ocean current, bandwidth being lesser, pressure of water being more, and delay during propagation as well as probability of error. These issues were overcome by the proposed work MCR-UWSN which stands for metaheuristics-based clustering in UWSN. The head of each cluster (Subramani et al. 2022) is selected based on CEPOC called as cultural emperor penguin optimizer-based clustering method. In case of routing, MHR-GOA termed as Multi hop routing with grasshopper optimization is used for optimizing the parameter set for input. The results are validated and prove the efficiency of the model. Table 2 represents location based as well as location free routing.

Table 2 Location Based Vs Location Free Routing

Location Based	Location Free
Every node in the network is aware of the geographic information regarding the network.	Every node in the network is not aware of the geographic information regarding the network.
The prerequisite includes computation of path and information related to the network.	They perform operations without knowledge of the node's location.
Flooding techniques for improving the delivery ratio of packets are not employed.	The delivery ratio is improvised using flooding techniques.
E.g. Vector-based forwarding	E.g. Depth-based routing

Researchers are focusing towards underwater scenarios and communication used for data transfer in such environments. Technologies such as sensors are used for monitoring such environments thereby constituting UWSN. Various problems

that are related to UWSN along with the solutions for every problem are being discussed (Sandhiyaa et al. 2021). Various applications of UWSN along with the standardization and features based on security are also discussed.

Sensor nodes are used for collection of data in UWSN and the communication among them can be either wired or wireless. Conventional protocols used for routing in UWSN provide poor performance. The research aims in improving the consumption of energy, decreasing the delay and also improving the delivery ratio of packets. BPSOP stands for Beckoning Penguin Swarm Optimization Protocol (Boopalan et al. 2021) is the proposed work which is based on the penguin characteristics. Its foraging behavior is utilized for identification of better routes for forwarding of packets. NS3 is used for evaluation and the results produced denote the better performance of the proposed work. Link establishment for communication in UWSN is a tedious task among the sensors. The transmission of data needs to be done by minimizing the delay and increasing the reliability. Bio Objective protocol (Persis et al. 2021) is proposed to overcome these issues. The protocols which are based on conventional systems as well as vectors suffer from certain limitations which result in failure of transmission thereby increasing the delay of packet delivery. Bio objective optimization deals with delay as well as route reliability for producing optimum routes. Modified greedy best first search heuristic is used for optimization and the protocol performs better compared to the existing ones based on the results obtained after simulation. The problem is NP-Hard and the effort made for computation is also minimal. UWSN plays a major role in the field of military and also in protecting marine environments along with monitoring

activities including seismic monitoring and seabed exploration. Various problems are associated with them and the research work aims in discussing (Kaschel et al. 2021) these issues with relevant solutions for all. The factors to be considered in case of UWSN are consumption of energy, node reliability, noise of the ocean, interference of signals and signal security. The researchers also discuss the protocols used for managing the energy consumption in an effective way in UWSN.

Water constitutes the major part of the earth and several areas in the underwater environment remain unexplored. The behavior of the ocean is monitored with the help of sensors used in UWSN. Studies confirm that most of the underwater environment remains unobserved. The information is transmitted using wireless communication channels for observing the ocean. Applications are monitored using this data that is sensed from UWSN. Key aspects in UWSN are discussed (Monika et al. 2021) along with the techniques used for communication. The techniques used for collection of data are also surveyed along with the architecture of UWSN. The performance of the system is analyzed based on the results obtained from conventional methods available for data collection. Table 3 denotes the communication types.

Table 3 Types of Communication with Applications

Applications of UWSN	Architecture Type	Level of Deployment	Type of Communication
Exploring natural resources	Four Dimensional	River level	Acoustic Waves
Exploring Pipelines	Two Dimensional	Pool level	Radio and Acoustic Waves
Flood Management	Four Dimensional	River level	Acoustic Waves
Earthquake Management	Three Dimensional	None	Acoustic Waves
Military Services using Submarine	Two Dimensional	Sea level	Acoustic Waves
Tsunami Management	Three Dimensional	None	Acoustic Waves
Military Services based on surveillance	Three Dimensional	Sea level	Wired Communication

In order to monitor as well as explore the ocean, underwater acoustic sensor networks are employed. The nodes are available in various depths of water. Those that are available deep in the sea are unable to perform communication with ones that are available on the sea surface. Constraints to be paid attention are delay being higher as well as attention being more. Void region presence affects the performance of the system. Nodes used as forwarders need to be selected for preventing this void region. This is done using the grey wolf optimization method thereby improving the lifetime of the network and energy balancing (Gola et al. 2021). MATLAB is used for simulating the results and compared with the routing protocols depending on depth. The ratio of packet delivery obtained for 96% and the size of the node is 180. The count of nodes that are dead is also reduced thereby achieving the goals of improved lifetime as well as delay reduction in transmission. The work is also analyzed with other metrics used for measuring the performance. Routing based on a multi-hop method is done using the clustering protocol in UWSN. The consumption of energy of the nodes can also be changed when the performance of the network is maintained in an excellent way. The proposed model works on EOCA (Yu et al. 2020) which stands for energy optimization

clustering algorithm where the communication among the nodes in a particular range takes place. The delay in transmission is computed by every node among the sink as well as sensor nodes followed by the selection of cluster head based on the delay value. Forwarder is chosen based on the node depth before the commencement of packet forwarding. These packets are forwarded either towards the cluster head or towards the sink. The consumption of energy of every node is also balanced in the proposed model.

The proposed model uses K-means methods for implementing S-BEAR (Wang et al. 2020) which stands for simplified balanced energy adaptive routing. IN random fashion, the heads of clusters are being elected. The joining of other nodes with these cluster heads is based on the computation of Euclid distance which needs to be minimal. Communication occurs among the nodes and the sink in a multi-hop manner.

UWSN consists of several nodes used for collection of data and it also suffers from certain limitations such as batteries that are not replaceable, communications including longer distances are being delayed and so on. UWSN also needs to concentrate on improving the lifetime along with the balancing of energy consumption for every node in the network. These problems can

be overcome by usage of methods such as clustering. Factors to be considered in clustering are cluster count, cluster formation along with the selection of head for every cluster. The model uses clustering technique with FCM (Fuzzy C-Means) method as well as MFO also called moth-flame optimization algorithm (Fei et al. 2020). This hybrid approach aims at improving the performance of the network. The cluster formation is performed using FCM methods followed by the selection process of cluster head being optimized by MFO algorithm. The proposed model is compared with the existing ones based on the performance of energy efficiency in UWSN.

One of the major issues of UWSN that needs to be addressed soon is control of energy. The nodes in UWSN can either be static or dynamic in nature. Issues related to performance may occur due to limited memory of the nodes, low battery, and communication occurring in shorter range as well as computation speed which is lesser. In order to forward the packets in a proper manner, routing protocol is necessary. The research work discusses EE- MDCHSRP which stands for energy efficient and mobility-based dynamic cluster head selection routing protocol (Gomathi et al. 2020) for choosing the heads of clusters in an effective manner. Density of nodes, energy being utilized along with the factor of mobility govern the selection process. The proposed model performs better than the traditional algorithms and the simulation results prove it. The research work aims in reducing the consumed power for every sensor node, the time taken for response and avoidance of overload. These factors in turn increase the throughput of UWSN along with its lifetime also.

Optimization methods are used for selection of routes in the protocol based on clustering mechanisms. Clusters are formed in UWSN and the selection of cluster heads is done based on the energy of every node in the network (Durrani et al. 2019). The protocol suffers from certain pitfalls such as latency being increased and the packets may also be duplicated at the end of the receiver node. These problems occur when the members of the cluster are being selected.

The deployment of the network gets partitioned as layers where every layer is identified with a separate value for depth and width of the area. The proposed protocol MLCEE (Khan et al. 2019) stands for multi-layer cluster-based energy efficient protocol that helps in improving the lifetime of the network by decreasing the delay in delivering the packets. Computation of layers is done by the node in this protocol followed by broadcasting the messages which helps in cluster formation. The role of node here is forwarder as there are several layers in the model and this forwarding process uses energy along with node probability.

The formation of clusters is done with the help of AUV (Khan et al. 2019) in UWSN. They were also used for selection of cluster heads; transmission of data being scheduled along with the cycle for wake up as well as sleep. Data collection process is dependent on AUV and the cluster heads wait to complete the process. This in turn increases the delay in packet delivery thereby increasing the time for waiting at the location of the cluster head.

The applications of UWSN are widespread including resource exploration present underwater, collection of data, surveillance as well as prevention of disasters that may occur naturally. Traditional WSN utilizes radio waves to perform communication whereas UWSN makes use of acoustic waves for this purpose. The usage of acoustic waves also faced various

issues including reduced bandwidth, delay of transmission being increased, loss of path as well as affected connectivity. Network lifetime can be improved by using certain algorithms and also batteries can also be employed. Flooding of packets occurs thereby reducing the lifetime of the network which are the challenges in UWSN.

Exploring the resources available underwater, collection of data, surveillance of activities and prevention of natural disaster are significant applications of UWSN. In the case of terrestrial networks, radio waves are employed for communicating among nodes whereas in UWSN, acoustic waves are employed. These acoustic channels also suffer from certain limitations including lower bandwidth and interrupted connectivity. E2MR, called as energy-efficient multipath routing, is proposed in UWSN for monitoring UWSN and for improving packet delivery (Muhammad et al. 2019). Priority table is established and the nodes forward packets based on this table. Other routing protocols are compared and analyzed with the proposed work to enhance the consumption of node energy and so on.

As there are water currents in the ocean, nodes of UWSN are not specific to a particular location. The data collected in UWSN needs to be transferred to various places and this can be performed by clustering the nodes. This in turn reduces the time taken for transmitting data. FSO stands for firefly swarm optimization is utilized for improvement of node stability (Viswa et al. 2019) as well as node proximity. The optimization algorithm plays a major role in reduction of network failure and the simulation performed proves the effectiveness of the system. The presence of void regions needs to be identified and removed for better performance of UWSN. Forwarder nodes are not available for sending the packets to the succeeding nodes if the void region is present. QoS (Quality of Service) dependent protocol for routing is proposed by the researchers for preventing this region (Gola et al. 2019). The information of the node is two-hop and the parameters used for analysis are information of depth, next distance, time for holding the packets. These parameters help in identification of a better forwarder node that plays a significant role in transfer of packets among sources as well the destination. MATLAB implementation provides improved performance compared with the conventional algorithms as the ratio of packet delivery is improved thereby reducing the dead node count.

The routing protocol is based on a clustering mechanism using factors such as depth as well as energy. EERBLC stands for energy-efficient routing protocol depending on layer as well as unequal clusters (Zhu et al. 2018) is proposed for selection of path for routing based on quality of link as well as energy of nodes. The location of anode is not necessary for setting a cluster. Cost computation is done based on the ratio of forwarding as well as residual energy. Header nodes are selected not only using timing but also the node location. Nodes acting as cluster heads for more time are chosen to be hotspots by attackers leading to their death also.

Another protocol proposed in UWSN is TCEB (Hong et al. 2018) which stands for topology control energy balance protocol. The selection of head for the cluster depends on the energy of the node and the loss of path. The protocol is non-cooperative in nature. Cluster head is selected with certain strategies and methods used by nodes in UWSN. Residual energy of a node and loss of path in distance of one-hop are denoted by a function called pay-off. The overall goal of the

protocol is balancing the consumption of energy for the nodes used in UWSN.

The proposed model uses EULC (Hou et al. 2018) called as energy balanced unequal layering clustering algorithm in UWSN for reduction of energy consumption. The size of the clusters differs when they are created with layers thereby solving issues such as hotspots. Layers are used for deployment of a network by using the radius of communication range being employed. Computation of weight is done using parameters such as node energy, sink distance as well as degree of the node. Cluster head is elected based on the weight computation and the one with more weight is chosen to be the head node. Information regarding the cluster head in the neighboring locations are used for computation of routing using the distance measure among the nodes as well as the energy consumption. The node whose value after computation is smallest is selected as the cluster head for the next hop communication.

The nodes depend on the battery life which is limited in UWSN. This results in isolation of few nodes and the packets that are buffered may be discarded. The forwarder nodes are selected based on the greedy algorithm which is mostly the node near the surface of sea. They relay data among the source as well as destination. The risk of energy is drained as selection of nodes occurs from various sources. The protocol enhancement is done where the task of forwarding is divided among the forwarder nodes that may be made available in the next hop. The adjustment of depth is yet another factor for solving the isolated node problem. The splitting process is carried out in the packet which acts as a source and every packet gets forwarded to the nearby nodes (Mohamed et al. 2018). Data channels are also employed for the process of eliminating the collision issues. The protocol performance is validated by implementation results and comparative analysis.

The protocols based on clustering strategy are analyzed with various factors such as stability of the cluster, efficiency of delay, balancing of load as well as efficiency of energy. The coverage needs to be maximum as the range of transmission is longer along with more node mobility (Sandeep et al. 2017). Selection of cluster heads by these protocols is done with the help of factors such as node position, packets generated, node priority, consumption of energy and so on. The protocols also aim is obtaining better performance and the delivery ratio of the packets is also higher. Additionally, the latency is lower and the lifetime of the network is longer.

UASN stands for Underwater Acoustic Sensor Networks and the clustering methods employed here suffer from certain pitfalls which affect their major functionalities. The model proposed is based on clustering where the power of transmission for every sensor node is considered along with the loads of cluster head and the energy consumed by the head (Pengwei et al. 2017). The algorithm performing clustering operation is dependent on the PSO. The nodes are clustered in a periodic manner and the selection of cluster heads is performed in a rotation manner. The results are generated after the performance of the simulation which reduces the consumption of energy, improved lifetime of the network as well as stability being increased.

The balance of energy needs to be maintained between the nodes for the lifespan of the network which is the main issue in case of UWSN. Proposed model works based on the BMOOR algorithm called Balanced Multi-objective Optimized Opportunistic Routing (Kanthimathi et al. 2017). Estimation is done in a dynamic way while considering energy and the

forwarders are chosen in the model. Spatial location is not necessary for this proposed work which reduces the expenditure incurred while deployment. It also avoids trapping of nodes and for optimization, Bat algorithm is employed. It minimizes the packet delay and maximizes the ratio of packet delivery. Fitness function enhances the lifetime of the network. NS2 simulation is performed which indicates the performance of the BMOOR.

Applications related with the underwater scenarios depending on wireless functionalities are related to UWSN. One of the difficult tasks for several applications are node deployment and constraints based on energy. The properties of water including its temperature and salinity and so on are taken in consideration along with the node layout in a physical manner while considering UWSN. There is a necessity for development of methodology which is computational intelligence dependent using the resources in an effective manner. The optimization method employed in the proposed model is the genetic algorithm (Iyer et al. 2015). The nodes in UWSN are positioned and deployed using the optimization technique for coverage maximization. Monitoring of the ocean for civil applications requires identification of nodes that are minimal along with their specified positions.

The researchers proposed a CARP called the Channel-aware Routing Protocol which aims to improve the quality of link for transfer of information (Stefano et al. 2015). Certain nodes are selected based on their transmission history. Loops are prevented here with the help of count of hops necessary to reach the destination. Control of power is also important in selection of links for forwarding the packets. The proposed protocol is compared with the traditional ones and the parameters used for performance analysis are latency, consumption of energy along with ratio of packet delivery. The simulation is performed using NS2 and the results obtained are promising.

Clusters in UWSN can be established using the LEACH protocol. The protocol used in the proposed system improvised LEACH and provided C-LEACH called Controlled LEACH (Li et al. 2014). Control nodes available at the network center location perform processing operations leading to the network lifetime being increased while compared with the traditional LEACH protocol. The proposed protocol suffers from certain limitations including increased processing time as the data needs to be transmitted among the control nodes as well as other nodes.

The proposed model works based on CVBF (Ibrahim et al. 2014) which stands for clustering vector based forwarding method. Here the clustering process takes place using a sink that is created virtually for every cluster formed. The space of the network is further subdivided as cuboids of equal length where every cuboid forms an individual cluster. Nodes adjacent to the sink acts as a virtual sink.

The characteristics of UWSN are volatile in nature which necessitates the need for routing protocol. The researchers developed DVRP called the Diagonal and Vertical Routing Protocol which utilizes the angle of flooding zone for transmitting the packets among the nodes (Tariq et al. 2014). The energy of every node in UWSN is also saved from saving the lifetime of the entire network. Packet forwarding is done based on flooding angle in order to maintain the energy of nodes in UWSN. Compared to other protocols, the proposed one obtained significant results. Table 4 presents the protocol comparison for clustering.

Table 4 Protocol Comparison for Clustering

Name of the Protocol	Parameter Selection	Dimensions of Network	Utilization of Energy
Low Energy Adaptive Clustering Hierarchy	Value selected in random	Two dimensional	Done
Depth Based Routing	Based on depth	Three dimensional	Done
Energy Efficient Routing Protocol Based on Layers and unequal Clusters	Value selected in random	Three dimensional	Done
Equalized Cluster Low Energy Adaptive Clustering Hierarchy	Based on distance and node location	Two dimensional	Done
Multi-Layer Cluster- based Energy Efficient Protocol	Based on fitness function	Three dimensional	Done
Topology Control with Energy Balance	Based on neighbours count	Two dimensional	Done
Energy Optimization Clustering Algorithm	Based on neighbours count, Sink distance	Two dimensional	Done
Energy-balanced Unequal Layering Clustering	Sink distance	Three dimensional	Done
Hybrid Energy Efficient Distributed	Based on node energy	Two dimensional	Done
Cluster based Energy Efficient Routing Protocol	Based on node energy	Three dimensional	Done
Clustering Vector- Based Forwarding	Based on Vector	Two dimensional	Done
Evidence-Efficient Multihop Clustering Routing	Based on hop count	Two dimensional	Done
Vector-Based Void Avoidance	Void Region	Two dimensional	Done

Apart from industries, UWSN also extends its applications in fields such as academics for exploration of resources. The width and the direction of dimensions are given importance in the proposed work which in turn improves the connectivity of the network. A mechanism for detecting the link is employed for obtaining the information regarding link along with adaptive routing feedback technique is utilized (Song et al. 2013). The routing protocol is based on credits which eliminates the need for table updation. The protocol feasibility is analyzed with various performance metrics along with existing work comparison. Transmission of data gets affected by the issues in UWSN such as lower bandwidth with less node energy. The proposed work AURP called the AUV-aided underwater routing protocol utilizes AUV for data communication among sensors (Yoon et al. 2012). The nodes chosen for relying on data are chosen to be AUV in the proposed protocol which works in a multi-hop fashion. This in turn improves the performance of the network as the delivery ratio of data is increased. The performance results after experiments denote the research goal being obtained.

The proposed protocol for UWSN is E-PULRP (Gopi et al. 2010) called as energy-optimized path unaware layered routing protocol. Layers are formed in the network and they are located near the sink. Every layer is identified with a relay node for forwarding the packets. Layered structure is created with the concentric shell for performing transmission with the help of a sink. Data is forwarded among the nodes as well as sink based on the path which is multi-hop in nature. Every layer also makes use of the relay node that is being chosen. The major goal of this protocol is preservation of consumed energy.

III. Conclusion

The sensor networks are having various applications nowadays and have emerged as a wide area of research. In the case of WSNs, their base station is located at a particular distance from the nodes and is employed for monitoring of the environment as well as military works. Due to various advancements, UWSNs have gained huge importance along with advancements. These sensors are smaller in size and use either radio waves or acoustic waves for communication. The main purpose of these sensors is collection of data and relaying the collected data to desired locations. In order to transfer data in a reliable way, there is a need for routing protocols to help the transmission. The literature

review presents the issues present in UWSN along with the survey of various routing protocols available for transfer of data. This identifies the pitfalls in existing works and necessitates the novel model for data transmission in UWSN.

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